

FLAMMABILITY OF NATURAL FIBRE-REINFORCED POLYMERIC COMPOSITES

Debes Bhattacharyya and Nam Kyeun Kim

Centre for Advanced Composite Materials, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Auckland, New Zealand, d.bhattacharyya@auckland.ac.nz and nam.kim@auckland.ac.nz

Keywords: Natural fibres, Composites flammability, Fire modelling

ABSTRACT

This paper presents thermal and flammability characteristics of natural fibre reinforced polymeric composites, which are being increasingly used for engineering applications. Cellulose and protein based fibres have been selected with thermoplastic and thermoset polymers to investigate their effects, in combination with halogen-free flame retardant (FR), on reaction-to-fire properties of the composites. Standard flammability test methods (e.g. cone calorimeter and UL-94) and thermogravimetric analysis have been employed to evaluate the fire performance and thermal decomposition of the materials, respectively. The combined effects of wool and FR on effective char formation of the wool-polypropylene composites have achieved a significant reduction in heat release and smoke production in the cone calorimeter test and self-extinguishment after the vertical flame application. Furthermore, a flax reinforced epoxy composite laminate has shown a comparable peak heat release rate to one of glass fibre counterpart by incorporating a suitable FR. Scanning electron microscope has also been adopted to observe char formed during the cone calorimeter test to identify the role of char structure in determining flammability. Finally, some results have been presented on the overall fire modelling of natural fibre composites using the Fire Dynamics Simulator package.

1 INTRODUCTION

Research and development of advanced composite materials including natural resources have been carried out intensively for their applications in infrastructure and transportation industries. Bio-based fibres have been employed as reinforcement or filler in the composites due to their flexibility during processing, high specific stiffness, biodegradability and low cost [1]. In particular, composites based on natural fibres and thermoplastic polymers can be recycled at the end of their life cycle and can preserve mechanical moduli after the recycling process [2]. Furthermore, the poor interfacial adhesion between hydrophilic fibre and hydrophobic polymer, that limited the desirable mechanical performance for the engineering applications, has been overcome by the fibre surface treatments or compatibilisers [3].

In spite of the aforementioned merits of natural fibre composites, high flammability of composites is a critical issue to restrict their uses in plastic industries. Poor fire resistance of polymers negatively affects the fire performance of composites; therefore extensive studies have been conducted on the thermal decomposition and fire resistance of polymeric materials to reduce their flammability. Among a variety of flame retardant methods including physical and chemical treatments, the addition of flame retardant (FR) has proven to be effective in controlling the fire. However, some of them containing halogens have negative effects on the environment and human health [4]. Thus, it is desirable to use an environment friendly fire retardant system for polymeric composites. Natural fibres are increasingly being considered as an alternative group of fibre reinforcement in composites due to their certain inherent advantages, namely biodegradability and CO₂ neutrality, over the synthetic materials. Wool as a natural protein fibre is a less flammable material because of its relatively high content of cysteine (10 wt%), which is a sulphur containing amino acid, and nitrogen (15-16 wt%) [5]. It has also been observed that wool fibres produce char in an intumescent manner upon combustion. On the other hand, lignocellulose fibres, such as flax and kenaf, are commonly thought as combustion sources in composites, but the fibres having high amount of lignin can be beneficial on char formation in the

presence of FR [6]. In particular, as a halogen-free intumescent FR, ammonium polyphosphate contains phosphorus and nitrogen, which can contribute to improved fire retardancy for the polymeric composites under combustion. Therefore, the fire growth can be controlled by selecting suitable combination of materials in the composites.

In this study, the effects of natural fibres on thermal and flammability characteristics of thermoplastic and thermoset polymer composites have been investigated by a set of comprehensive experiments. Flax (plant-based) and wool (animal-based) fibres have been used with polypropylene (PP) to produce short fibre composites and flax woven fabric has been employed for thermoset composite laminates. The cone calorimeter has demonstrated the fire reaction properties, such as heat release and smoke production, and the vertical burn test has identified burning behaviour of composites. In addition, microstructures of fire residues have been observed using an environmental scanning electron microscope (ESEM). Tensile and flexural properties of composites have been discussed to explore the impact of FR on mechanical performance. Furthermore, Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS) package has created the combustion models of natural fibre composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 MATERIALS

Flax yarn for a short fibre composite was supplied by Bruce Smith Ltd. (New Zealand) and flax woven fabric (2x2 twill weave) for a composite laminate was obtained from Libero (Belgium). Coarse wool fibres were provided by Bloch & Behrens Ltd. (New Zealand) after a scouring process to delete impurities on fibre surface. Commercial PP (HP400L, LyondellBasell, New Zealand) and DGEBA epoxy resin (105 West System epoxy, Adhesive Technologies Ltd, New Zealand) were selected as thermoplastic and thermoset polymer matrices, respectively. Moreover, a coupling agent for interfacial adhesion between fibre and polymer was maleic anhydride grafted polypropylene (MAPP - Licocene 6452). FRs used for thermoplastic and thermoset polymer composites were Budit[®]3167 and FR CROS 40 intumescent flame retardants, respectively, from Budenheim in Germany.

2.2 COMPOSITES PREPARATION

A granulator cut wool and flax fibres into short form with an average length of 2.9 mm. After drying the short fibres, PP and other additives, namely MAPP and FR, at 75 °C, a twin-screw extruder was employed for melt-blending of the constituents at an average processing temperature of 175 °C. The compound pellets were then processed using the Boy 50A injection moulding machine to produce composites for evaluating fire and mechanical characteristics. An injection pressure was approximately 85 bar (8.5 MPa) and the temperature profile from a feeder to nozzle was 150/185/185/180 °C. Weight percentages of fibre, MAPP and FR in composites were 25, 3 and 15 wt%, respectively.

A hand lay-up process was executed to manufacture fibre reinforced composite laminates. Nine layers of flax woven fabric were piled up after impregnating each layer with a mixture of epoxy resin and hardener (weight ratio of 5.4:1). A press was then used to cure the composite at 0.7 MPa pressure for 72 h. FR particles were mixed with the resin (weight ratio of 1:5) using a high shear mixer (Silverson, US). The composite laminates had an average of 2.6 mm thickness with fibre volume percentage of 34.5 %.

2.3 CHARACTERISATION METHODS

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA-50, Shimadzu, Japan) was implemented to investigate thermal decomposition of the constituents and composites. Weight loss of a sample (around 7 mg) was measured from ambient temperature to 700 °C at constant rate of 10 °C/min. Furthermore, a vertical burn test was performed to observe burning behaviour of sample. ASTM D638 protocol (equivalent to UL-94) was selected for sample preparation, testing procedure and classification of results into grades, namely V-0 (the best rating), V-1, V-2 and no rating (NR). Fire reaction properties of samples were also obtained by a cone calorimeter (FTT Ltd, East Grinstead, UK), Figure 1(a). ASTM E1354 was chosen for the

equipment calibration and testing procedure, and a sample was mounted horizontally under 50 kW/m^2 heat flux. Heat release and smoke production rates were measured by a paramagnetic oxygen analyser and smoke obscuration system, respectively. Additionally, Federal Aviation Regulation (FAR) was applied to assess heat release rates (HRRs) of the composite laminates. The Ohio State University calorimeter has generally been used for testing the aircraft interiors, but the current study used the cone calorimeter as an available equipment to set up a cone heater and sample holder vertically to evaluate the heat releases of composite laminates, Figure 1(b). Moreover, micro-structures of char residues remaining after the cone calorimeter test were observed by ESEM. A universal testing machine (Instron 5567, UK) measured the tensile and flexural properties, based on ASTM D638 and ASTM D790, respectively. A video extensometer detected the extension of sample under tension and the tensile moduli were calculated between 0.05 % and 0.25 % strains. For flexural moduli and strengths, a span length of 45 mm and cross-head speed of 12 mm/min were selected.

Figure 1: (a) Cone calorimeter and (b) vertical orientation of cone heater and sample

2.4 FIRE SIMULATION

Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS), as a computational fluid dynamics code of fire-driven fluid flow, was adopted to simulate the cone calorimeter test of the natural fibre composites. The simulation package is an efficient software designed to solve Navier-Stokes equations appropriate for thermally driven flow [7]. Figure 2 shows a schematic diagram regarding the reactions of thermal decomposition and combustion of a material during the fire exposure [8]. In the current study, an FDS code was developed to predict the HRR of the composites as a major parameter in the combustion process. Boundary conditions based on the cone calorimeter set-up were applied to the model and material properties (e.g. physical and thermal) were used for the burning process simulation.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of thermal decomposition and combustion reactions (adapted from [8]).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 THERMAL DECOMPOSITION

Thermogravimetric (TG) curves of neat PP, natural fibres (i.e. flax and wool), natural fibre-PP composites and natural fibre-PP-FR composites are demonstrated in Figure 3(a). The neat PP is thermally decomposed without any residues and its onset temperature of the decomposition is around 320 °C. Flax and wool fibres show an initial weight loss step at approximately 100 °C due to the moisture evaporation, whereas wool has higher amount of residue (~28 %) at 700 °C and slower decomposition rate than those of flax fibres. Moreover, the wool-PP composite produces char after the decomposition test because of the charring tendency of wool. The influence of intumescent FR on the thermal decomposition is also clearly observed in the TG curves of both wool-PP-FR and flax-PP-FR composites. In particular, the combined effect of flax and FR on the char formation is identified by the notable increase in the residue amount from 0.21 to 14.3 %, Figure. 3(a). It can be noted that the hydroxyl group of lignocellulose in flax can react with phosphoric acids of the ammonium polyphosphate based FR to form the char [5].

Figure 3: Thermogravimetric curves of (a) neat PP, natural fibres and various types of composites [9] and (b) neat epoxy, flax, E-glass and various types of composites.

The thermal decomposition of the flax reinforced epoxy composite laminate is compared with that of glass fibre counterpart, Figure 3(b). Glass fibre, as a thermally inert material, does not show any weight loss during the test. The TGA curve of epoxy resin has a sharp drop of weight, but the cross-

linked structure of the thermosetting resin yields approximately 10 % residue under nitrogen atmosphere. Moreover, the incorporation of char forming additives in glass-epoxy and flax-epoxy composites significantly increases the amount of residue.

3.2 VERTICAL BURN TEST

Vertical burning behaviour of neat PP and composites was classified into different grades based on the UL-94 standard [9]. Neat PP, wool-PP and flax-PP composites completely burnt after the first flame application, therefore the samples could not be rated (NR). On the contrary, the wool-PP-FR composite achieved the self-extinguishment after two 10s flame applications, thereby resulting in V-0. However, the flax-PP-FR composite had a continuous burning up to the holding clamp. It can indicate that char forming ability of wool enhanced the fire retardancy of the composite in the presence of the intumescent flame retardant. Even though the positive effect of flax and FR on the thermal stability of composite was identified in the TGA result, the char formed from the composite was not rigid enough to impede the flame spread under the direct flame application.

The flammability of flax-epoxy and flax-epoxy-FR composite laminates was also evaluated by the vertical burn test based on FAR. More severe testing condition (60 s flame application) than UL-94 was applied to the samples, but the result of flax-epoxy-FR composite met the FAR requirement of the vertical burn test. Burning length and time of the composite were 59 mm and 14 s which were less than the required values of 152.4 mm and 15 s, respectively. As the neat epoxy resin formed char, the more rigid and condensed char formed while using flax-epoxy-FR (in comparison to the char for flax-PP-FR composite) suppressed the flame spread and contributed to the flame-extinguishment. Interestingly, the result was comparable to that of glass-epoxy-FR composite.

3.3 CONE CALORIMETER

The neat PP shows the highest peak heat release rate (PHRR) due to its high flammability, whereas wool-PP and flax-PP composites have lower PHRR than one of neat PP, Figure 4(a). The addition of natural fibres reduces the HRRs but both the composites still burn vigorously under the cone heater. On the other hand, the composites having natural fibres and intumescent FR achieve a significant decrease (approx. 70%) in PHRR compared to one of neat PP. In particular, the combined effect of wool and FR on suppressing combustion is more dominant than that of flax-PP-FR composite. The effective char formation from wool and FR induces lower PHRR with an increased time to reach PHRR wool-PP-FR composite. SPR graphs, Figure 4(b), also present the similar trend with HRR curves.

Figure 4: (a) Heat release rate and (b) smoke production rate curves of neat PP, natural fibres-PP and natural fibres-PP-FR composites (horizontal sample orientation) [9].

HRR curves of the composite laminates, Figure 5(a), show more fluctuations than those of short fibre composites due to their layer-by-layer structures. Moreover, as glass fibre is thermally inert, the glass-epoxy composite ignites later and releases heat and smoke more slowly than flax-epoxy composite during the combustion process. On the contrary, the presence of FR in flax-epoxy composite leads to more dramatic reduction of HRR and SPR because of the combined effect of flax and FR on the char formation. Reaction between hydroxyl group of flax and phosphoric acids of FR contributes on the effective char formation, therefore the char can play an essential role in diminishing heat and smoke of the composite, Figure 5. Heat radiation penetrated through the composite's layers still causes the unstable heat release rate in spite of the char.

Figure 5: (a) Heat release rate and (b) smoke production rate curves of natural fibres-epoxy resin and natural fibres-epoxy resin-FR composites (vertical sample orientation).

The char formed during the cone calorimeter test was also observed in ESEM. The microstructures of wool-PP-FR and flax-PP-FR char are shown in Figures 6(a) and (b), respectively. The wool-PP-FR composite forms more closed and condensed char structure than one of flax-PP-FR composite. The porous structure of char produced from flax-PP-FR composite is one of the major reasons to release more heat and smoke than wool-PP-FR composite during the cone calorimeter test.

Figure 6: ESEM images of inner surfaces of char: (a) wool-PP-FR and (b) flax-PP-FR composites.

3.4 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The moduli and strengths of neat PP and composites are shown in Figures 7(a) and (b), respectively. The effective fibre distribution and good fibre-polymer interfacial adhesion improve the strengths and tensile/flexural stiffness values of natural fibre-PP composites. In general, flax-PP composites have higher mechanical properties than those of wool-PP composites because of the superior mechanical performance of flax fibres [9]. In addition, the positive effect of FR on tensile modulus is identified in Figure 5(a) as the FR additives are fairly rigid [5]. Nevertheless, the addition of FR reduces both tensile and flexural strengths of the composites, Figure 7(b). The existence of FR particles can create stress concentration during the test or can deteriorate the interfacial bonding between the fibre and polymer constituents, thereby losing the composites strengths [5, 10]. However, the tensile and flexural strengths of wool-PP-FR and flax-PP-FR composites are still higher than those of neat PP due to the affirmative influence of MAPP coupling agent on the adhesion.

Figure 7: Tensile and flexural properties of PP, natural fibre-PP and natural fibre-PP-FR composites: (a) modulus and (b) strength [9].

3.5 FIRE MODELLING

Heat release rates of composites simulated by FDS are demonstrated with the experimental results in Figure 8. The curves show that the simulated PHRRs of both flax-PP and wool-PP composites are higher than the experimental values. The results can be attributed to the fact that the effect of MAPP on the heat release rate was not applied into the FDS model. The previous research of the authors has shown that the improved interfacial adhesion between the fibre and polymer due to MAPP requires more energy to pull apart the constituents and reduces HRR under the combustion process [6]. However, the FDS was limited to define the interfacial adhesion of the constituents, thus the simulated PHRR values do not match well with the experimental results. On the other hand, the HRR curves of wool-PP composite show more or less similar trends between the numerical and experimental studies until the HRR drops by the flameout. In the cone calorimeter result, the initial shoulder-like curve at around 80 s is mostly due to the formation of residues by wool. In FDS, lower activation energy and pre-exponential factor of wool, which were measured by TGA, compared to those of neat PP induces the slower heat release rate. Furthermore, the second peak around 170 s at both curves can be ascribed to the further combustion of composite and rebounding heat radiation from back surface of the sample holder. The char formed during the test in reality postpones the combustion period, thus the simulation of char formation is also highly required to enhance the accuracy of the FDS model.

Figure 8: HRR curves obtained from FDS and experimental studies.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The present work has mainly demonstrated the thermal and flammability characteristics of natural fibre reinforced polymeric composites. The TGA results have identified the combined effect of natural fibre and intumescent FR on forming residues and reducing the decomposition rate. In particular, flax-epoxy-FR composite has retained around 30 wt% of residues at 700 °C. Moreover, the flax-epoxy-FR composite laminate has met the requirement of FAR vertical burn test for aircraft interiors and the inherent fire resistant behaviour of wool has also allowed the thermoplastic composite to achieve V-0 classification at the UL-94 vertical burn test. In the cone calorimeter tests, the fire reaction properties, namely HRR and SPR, of wool-PP-FR composites are lower than those of flax-PP-FR composites due to the closed and condensed char structure formed during the test. On the other hand, the flax-epoxy-FR composite has shown the comparable fire reaction properties to those of glass-epoxy-FR composites. The presence of FR in the natural fibre composites is detrimental to the interfacial adhesion between fibre and polymer, thereby adversely affecting the tensile and flexural strengths, but still maintaining the higher composite strengths. Additionally, the FDS model, which was developed to simulate the cone calorimeter test, has specified HRRs of the natural fibre composites and has demonstrated a reasonable agreement with the experimental results of wool-PP composites.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the support from Ministry of Business, Innovation & Employment (UOAX 1004) and Wool Industry Research Limited (CP2013_25) of New Zealand.

REFERENCES

- [1] O. Faruk, A.K. Bledzki, H.P. Fink, M. Sain, Biocomposites reinforced with natural fibers: 2000–2010, *Progress in Polymer Science*, **37**, 2012, pp. 1552-1596.
- [2] A. Bourmaud, C. Baley, Rigidity analysis of polypropylene/vegetal fibre composites after recycling, *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, **94**, 2009, pp. 297-305.
- [3] M.M. Kabir, H. Wang, K.T. Lau, F. Cardona, Chemical treatments on plant-based natural fibre reinforced polymer composites: An overview, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **43**, 2012, pp. 2883-2892.
- [4] B. Lecouvet, M. Sclavons, C. Bailly, S. Bourbigot, A comprehensive study of the synergistic flame retardant mechanisms of halloysite in intumescent polypropylene, *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, **98**, 2013, pp. 2268-2281.

- [5] N.K. Kim, R.J.T. Lin, D. Bhattacharyya, Effects of wool fibres, ammonium polyphosphate and polymer viscosity on the flammability and mechanical performance of PP/wool composites, *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, **119**, 2015, pp. 167-177.
- [6] N.K. Kim, D. Bhattacharyya, Development of fire resistant wool polymer composites: Mechanical performance and fire simulation with design perspectives, *Materials & Design*, **106**, 2016, pp. 391-403.
- [7] K. McGrattan, S. Hostikka, J. Floyd, R. McDermott, Fire dynamics simulator (version 6), technical reference guide. NIST special publication, 2014, pp. 1-149.
- [8] A.P. Mouritz, S. Feih, E. Kandare, Z. Mathys, A.G. Gibson, P.E. Des Jardin, S.W. Case, B.Y. Lattimer. Review of fire structural modelling of polymer composites. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **40**, 2009, pp. 1800-1814.
- [9] N.K. Kim, R.J.T. Lin, D. Bhattacharyya, Flammability and mechanical behaviour of polypropylene composites filled with cellulose and protein based fibres: a comparative study, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **100**, 2017, pp. 215-226.
- [10] N.K. Kim, R.J.T. Lin, D. Bhattacharyya, Extruded short wool fibre composites: Mechanical and fire retardant properties, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **67**, 2014, pp. 472-480.